

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

4th TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Effect of THERMAL DEGRADATION on the thermophysical properties of organic PCM
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	THERMADEG-PCM
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	ThermStore lab at AIT
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	latent heat storage, phase change materials, material degradation, material characterization
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	15/06/2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	30/06/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	17/06/2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	28/06/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	4
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Weekend
Number of days using the RI	10
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The project aimed to investigate the variation of the most relevant thermophysical properties of thermally degraded phase change materials (PCM) by applying different techniques. The materials studied were different fatty acids with melting temperatures below 100 °C (monocarboxylic) and around 150 °C (dicarboxylic), all with melting enthalpies around 200 kJ/kg. These PCM were subjected to isothermal tests under stress conditions for different temperatures and times and it was observed that all of them underwent chemical degradation with the formation of new organic products. Therefore, it was very important to study the influence of the degradation products on the thermophysical properties mentioned above. In this sense the ThermStore lab at AIT has not only the experimental facilities but also the expertise in measuring those properties.</p>	

The main expected outcome of this project was to obtain the evolution curves of the thermophysical properties with temperature and time in order to predict their variation during the lifetime of the PCM under operating conditions. Additionally, thermogravimetric (TG) measurements were proposed as well with the aim of having a preliminary estimation of the degradation kinetics of the dicarboxylic acids and also a comparison between the results obtained with AIT apparatus and other TG set-ups.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The work carried out during TNA was the one planned in the project proposal, which was divided in two different tasks. Task 1, whose objective was to study the variation of the relevant thermophysical properties (melting temperature, T_{melt} , melting enthalpy, ΔH_{melt} and thermal conductivity, λ) of various PCM after thermal tests under stress conditions. Task 2, whose objective was to carry out the kinetic analysis of possible degradation processes of some PCM by using TGA measurements. The PCM tested in these Tasks were different kinds of fatty acids that can be grouped in low melting temperature (<100 °C) monocarboxylic acids (lauric, myristic and stearic) and medium melting temperature (~150 °C) dicarboxylic acids (succinic, adipic, suberic and sebacic), all of them having melting enthalpies around 200 kJ/kg.

In Task 1, lauric, myristic and stearic acid (monocarboxylic) and also adipic acid (dicarboxylic) had to be studied. These PCM were already tested by CIEMAT under isothermal stress conditions under air at different temperatures and time intervals. Apart from evaporation, all of them showed a color change (from white to yellow, orange or brown) after the isothermal tests, which indicates that they undergo chemical degradation with the formation of new products, some of them colored. These degraded samples were analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in order to evaluate whether the products formed upon thermal tests had some effect on the PCM thermophysical properties (T_{melt} and ΔH_{melt}). For the case of thermal conductivity, λ , we realized that our samples did not meet the requirements for the corresponding THB technique and hence it would have been very difficult to obtain reliable results. Therefore, both user and host we agreed not to carry out this kind of characterization and focus on DSC measurements. DSC measurements were performed according to the protocols established in the host lab for this characterization technique so that the reliability of the results could be ensured. The user was charged of sample preparation and could carry out the measurements under the guidance and help of the RI staff. Since DSC apparatus had an automatic sampler, measurements of several samples could be programmed and done overnight, which really helped meeting the planned schedule. According to the project, 63 samples should be measured by DSC including both degraded and non-degraded samples of the four fatty acids mentioned above. In the end, it was possible to measure up 76 samples which included additional degraded samples, the other non-degraded dicarboxylic acids and also three additional PCM based on Polyethylene glycol (PEG3000, PEG6000 and PEG12000).

In relation to Task 2, TG measurements were carried out for all non-degraded PCM: monocarboxylic acids, dicarboxylic acids and PEG. These measurements were performed under air at different heating rates (2, 5, 10 and 20 K/min) so that they can be used for calculating the degradation kinetics of these PCM. The user was charged of sample preparation and could carry out the measurements under the guidance of the RI staff and according to the protocols established in the lab. Also, in this case the apparatus had an automatic sampler which made possible to accomplish all the planned measurements. In total 42 measurements were carried out: 4 heating rates x 10 PCM+ 2 repeated.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

In Task 1, DSC measurements were carried out for all the samples at 10 K/min with two heating and cooling runs. The first outcome of these measurements was the calculation of both melting temperature (T_{melt}) and enthalpy (ΔH_{melt}) by analysing the curves of the second heating/cooling run. These calculations were done with the analysis software of the DSC apparatus. In Figure 1, examples of the curves for both lauric and stearic acids before and after isothermal test @ 200 °C for 5 h are displayed together with the corresponding values of melting/freezing temperature and enthalpy.

Figure 1. Analysis of DSC curves for lauric and stearic acid samples before and after isothermal test for 5 h @ 200 °C.

As we can see, an important decrease of both T_{melt} and ΔH_{melt} is observed for these fatty acids after the isothermal test. This test was designed to achieve a high concentration of degradation products so their effect on the thermal properties could be more clearly observed. The rest of samples that were submitted to isothermal test for other temperatures and times also showed a decrease of these thermophysical properties but in a lower extent. The relationship between the experimental conditions of the tests and the values of T_{melt} and ΔH_{melt} will require a further and deeper analysis of DSC results. For the other fatty acids studied (myristic and adipic), also a decrease in the values of T_{melt} and ΔH_{melt} after the isothermal tests was observed.

In Task 2, TG measurements were carried out for all the planned PCM at different heating rates. In Figure 2 we can see the example of the measurements for the succinic acid: mass loss curve on the left and dTG curve in (1/°C vs T) on the right. The kinetic analysis of these curves should give information about the degradation kinetics of the PCM studied. This analysis requires some time and will be carried out in the future.

Figure 2. Mass loss and dTG curves obtained from TG measurements for the case of succinic acid.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

According to the preliminary analysis of DSC measurements carried out for the PCM samples submitted to test under thermal stress conditions, it is clear that both the thermophysical properties T_{melt} and ΔH_{melt} decrease as testing time and temperature are increased. This confirms the initial hypothesis of the project, which is that thermal degradation of these PCM implies the formation of new species which produce such decrease. As can be seen in Figure 1 it is interesting to note that the degraded samples only show a single DSC peak in both heating and cooling runs so that it is not possible to determine if this decrease is due to one or more new species. It might be interesting to carry out measurements at lower heating rates in order to increase the peak resolution and try to determine whether one or more species different from the non-degraded PCM are present. In any case this is only a preliminary interpretation of the results and we hope to have more information about the degradation of the PCM studied when both DSC and TG measurements are further analysed.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The main achievement of the work carried out during the TNA is that the thermal degradation of PCM based on fatty acids (both low-temp monocarboxylic and mid-temp dicarboxylic) has an impact in the relevant thermophysical properties for latent heat storage applications (i. e. T_{melt} and ΔH_{melt}). This impact is the decrease of these properties in comparison with the initial values displayed by the PCM. This is most probably due to the formation of degradation products with lower values of T_{melt} and ΔH_{melt} . In a preliminary analysis the degraded samples showed 28% melting enthalpy decrease in the case of lauric acid and 33 % in the case of stearic acid. However, it must be taken into account that the samples analysed were tested under quite strong stress conditions and hence, it may be possible that for some of the PCM studied, this decrease will not be observed when they will work under the service conditions of the storage system. This is expected to be confirmed after the analysis of DSC measurements is completed.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

Since the work to be carried out during the TNA was very well defined in advance, no difficulties were encountered for developing the activities of the project. Samples arrived on time, all the apparatus were ready and worked properly so that all planned samples could be measured. Also, the staff of the lab was always available for helping and solving any arising question/issue. Just to mention here that in the project it was expected to perform measurements of thermal conductivity, however, since our samples did not meet the requirements for the corresponding THB technique, user and host we agreed not to carry out this kind of characterization. In contrast, DSC and TGA measurements were carried out for more samples than initially planned in the project schedule.

Intended publications

We intend to publish the results of this TNA in one or more scientific conferences in the field of thermal storage materials and also in at least one scientific paper in a peer reviewed journal. As said in the project proposal, these results would complete the previous investigation carried out by CIEMAT in terms of the validation and assessment of the studied PCM.

Data management					
The data generated in this TNA are stored by the host lab according to their internal procedures and records but during the TNA we also agreed that they would be included in a database of PCM characterization the host lab is currently developing.					
Conclusions / additional comments					
In conclusion it can be said that TNA was highly successful since not only the planned work could be accomplished but also additional measurements were carried out. Moreover, I would like to thank very much the AIT and the ThermStore lab staff for their help and commitment and also highlight their professional skills, which strongly contributed to the success of the project.					
Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify				

	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.